

EBFMC25-OOP-10 · Prognostic Value of ACEF Score in the Detection of Contrast-Induced Nephropathy After Carotid Artery Stenting

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Contrast-induced nephropathy (CIN) is a complication associated with increased mortality and morbidity after percutaneous cardiac and non-cardiac vascular interventions (Paraskevas & Mikhailidis, 2017; Shoukat et al., 2010). Age, creatinine and left ventricular ejection fraction (ACEF) score has prognostic significance in cardiovascular diseases (Di Serafino et al., 2014; Lee et al., 2015). In our study, we aimed to determine the role of ACEF score in predicting the risk of CIN development in patients undergoing carotid artery stenting (CAS) for symptomatic carotid artery disease (CAD).

Materials and Methods: Patients who underwent CAS between 2021 and 2024 were retrospectively analysed. Patients were divided into two groups according to the occurrence of CIN after CAS. Baseline demographics and pre-procedure laboratory tests were compared between CIN groups. The diagnostic value of the ACEF score for predicting CIN after CAS was assessed by receiver operating characteristics (ROC) analysis. Risk factors for the development of CIN after CAS were determined by logistic regression analysis.

Results: The mean age of the 165 patients included in our study was 67.5 ± 9.8 years and 71.5% were male. Patients in the CIN (+) group (n = 21) were significantly older compared to those in the CIN (-) group (n = 143), and diabetes and hypertension were more frequent. Creatinine, neutrophils and C-reactive protein were higher, left ventricular ejection fraction (LVEF) and albumin were lower in the CIN (+) group compared to the CIN (-) group. ACEF score was significantly higher in the CIN (+) group (Table 1).

Table 1

Clinical, demographic, laboratory and echocardiographic parameters of all groups

Variables	CIN (+) n = 21	CIN (-) n = 143	p-value
Age	72,4 ± 9,7	67,4 ± 10.2	0.008
Gender, male, n (%)	15 (71.4%)	103 (72%)	0.205
Smoking, n (%)	8 (38.1%)	53 (37%)	0.411
BMI, kg/m ²	25.6 ± 5.2	26.7 ± 5.8	0.138
DM, n (%)	13 (61.9 %)	58 (40.5%)	0.01
Hypertension, n (%)	16 (76.1%)	85 (59.4%)	0.008
CAD, n (%)	9 (42.8%)	65 (45.4%)	0.604
HL, n (%)	11 (52.3%)	79 (55.2%)	0.235
LVEF, %	44.9 ± 8.2	52.8 ± 9.5	< 0.001
Creatinine, mg/dL	1.48 ± 0.32	1.01 ± 0.28	0.009
Sodium, mEq/L	141.5 ± 28.2	143.1 ± 27.9	0.781
Potassium, mEq/L	4.6 ± 0.82	4.5 ± 0.94	0.362
Glucose, mg/dL	142.9 ± 28.4	138.4 ± 27.6	0.388
Albumin, g/dL	3.6 ± 0.84	4.7 ± 0.93	< 0.001
TC, mg/dL	189.4 ± 37.8	184.9 ± 36.5	0.101
LDL, mg/dL	101.6 ± 21.3	109.3 ± 20.8	0.097
HDL, mg/dL	40.4 ± 8.3	45.6 ± 9.4	0.564
Haemoglobin, g/dL	13.2 ± 3.9	12.9 ± 3.7	0.482
Platelets, 10 ³ /μl	232.8 ± 45.5	241.2 ± 44.9	0.329
Neutrophils, 10 ³ /μl	5.4 ± 0.88	3.9 ± 0.68	0.012
Lymphocytes, 10 ³ /μl	3.4 ± 0.68	3.9 ± 0.72	0.466
CRP, mg/L	17.4 ± 3.2	5.9 ± 1.1	0.009
ACEF score	1.54 ± 0.32	1.12 ± 0.22	< 0.001

CIN: Contrast-induced nephropathy, BMI: Body mass index, DM: Diabetes mellitus, CAD: Coronary artery disease, HL: Hyperlipidemia, LVEF: Left ventricular ejection fraction, TC: Total cholesterol, LDL: Low-density lipoprotein cholesterol, HDL: High-density lipoprotein cholesterol, CRP: C-reactive protein, ACEF: Age, creatinine and left ventricular ejection fraction

Variables with a p-value < 0.1 in the univariate regression analysis were included in the multiple regression analysis model. The following factors were identified as independent risk factors for the development of CIN after CAS: age (odds ratio [OR]: 1.13, 95% confidence interval [CI]: 1.04 - 1.19, p: 0.009), creatinine (OR: 3.19, 95% CI: 2.08 - 6.87, p < 0.001), LVEF (OR: 0.93, 95% CI: 0.88 - 0.98, p: 0.018) and ACEF score (OR: 3.86, 95% CI: 2.13 - 6.19, p: 0.005) (Table 2).

Table 2

Evaluation of the ACEF score and its components in the development of CIN after CAS

	Odds Ratio	95% CI	p-value
Age	1.13	1.04 – 1.19	0.009
LVEF	0.93	0.88 – 0.98	0.018
Creatinine	3.19	2.08 – 6.87	< 0.001
ACEF score	3.86	2.13 – 6.19	0.005

ACEF: Age, creatinine and left ventricular ejection fraction, CIN: Contrast-induced nephropathy, CAS: Carotid artery stenting, CI: Confidence interval, LVEF: Left ventricular ejection fraction

According to the results of the ROC analysis, the ACEF score demonstrated a high level of diagnostic capability in predicting the development of CIN following CAS, with a sensitivity of 73% and a specificity of 78% at a predictive value of 1.32 (area under the curve [AUC]: 0.79, 95% CI: 0.70 - 0.86, p < 0.001).

Conclusion: The ACEF score is independently associated with post-procedural CIN in patients undergoing CAS for symptomatic CAD. The ACEF score has diagnostic power for predicting the development of CIN after CAS.

PEER REVIEW STATEMENT

This paper has undergone a double-blind peer review process and has been approved by the scientific committee of the conference.

KEYWORDS

ACEF score, carotid artery stenting, contrast-induced nephropathy

CONFLICT OF INTEREST DECLARATION

There is no commercial, financial, or personal conflict of interest in this study.

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